

SEARCH FOR NEW FILARICIDES

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Sixteen substituted *N*-piperidino- and *N*-morpholino-ethyl-*N*-alkoxypropylamines (analogous of hetrazan) have been synthesised with a view to testing their antifilarial activity.

Although 1-diethyl-4-carbamylpiperazine, commonly known as hetrazan, is an effective drug for the treatment of filariasis, it has no action on the adult worms or on the microfilariae present in the hydrocele fluid, being effective only against microfilariae present in the blood stream. It also produces severe allergic reactions and toxic symptoms.

It has been shown that neither the piperazine ring by itself nor its 1-methyl derivative has any antifilarial activity whereas 4-diethylcarbamylpiperazine has a high order of activity.

Besides hetrazan, the only compound, which was found to possess antifilarial activity by Sewell and Hawkings (*Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1950, 5, 239), was *NNN*-trimethyl-*N'*-diethylcarbamyl-ethylenediamine.

This led to the synthesis of a number of substituted ethylenediamines by Wadia *et al.* (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 17 C, 11) which may be considered as straight-chain analogues of hetrazan, retaining the basic centres for hydrogen bonding and providing a range of electron potentials on the component nitrogen atoms in the molecule.

The present investigation also reports the synthesis of substituted *N*-piperidino- and *N*-morpholino-ethyl-*N*-alkoxypropylamines which have been prepared by the condensation of piperidino- or morpholino-ethyl chloride hydrochlorides with ethoxy- and methoxy-propylamines. These have been converted into the corresponding ethoxycarbonyl, phenylcarbamoyl, and phenylisothiocarbamoyl derivatives.

N-Piperidinoethyl and *N*-morpholinoethyl chloride hydrochlorides were obtained by the action of thionyl chloride on piperidinoethanol and morpholinoethanol, following the method of Landenberg (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 1877).

Ethoxy- and methoxy-propylamines were prepared by the reduction of ethoxy- and methoxy-propionitriles, which were obtained by the method of Utermohlen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1505).

Condensation of *N*-piperidino- and morpholino-ethyl-*N*-alkoxypropylamines with ethyl chloroformate yielded the ethoxycarbonyl derivatives, and similarly condensation of these amines with phenyl isocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate in benzene afforded the corresponding phenylcarbamoyl and phenylisothiocarbamoyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Piperidinoethanol was prepared according to the method of Landenberg (*loc. cit.*) from piperidine (32 g.) and ethylene chlorohydrin (15 g.), b.p. 199°, yield 19 g.

N-Morpholinoethanol was obtained according to the method of Cumming *et al.* (*Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 4389) from morpholine (34 g.) and ethylene chlorohydrin (15.5 g.), b.p. 220°, yield 20 g.

Piperidinoethyl chloride hydrochloride was prepared from *N*-piperidinoethanol (12 g.) and thionyl chloride, m.p. 226°, yield 14 g.

N-Morpholinoethyl chloride hydrochloride was obtained from *N*-morpholinoethanol (8 g.) and thionyl chloride (8.5 g.), m.p. 180°, yield 10 g.

β -(*N'*-Piperidinoethyl or *N'*-morpholinoethyl)-*N*-ethoxycarbonyl-(*N'*-alkoxypropyl)-amine.— A mixture of *N*-piperidino- or *N*-morpholino-ethylalkoxypropylamine (0.1 *M*), anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.1 *M*), and ethanol (absolute, 50 c.c.) was stirred continuously and a solution of ethyl chloroformate (0.066 *M*) in 20 c.c. ethanol was added dropwise over a period of 2 hours. The reaction mixture was gently refluxed on a water bath with stirring for a further period of 3 hours, cooled, the solvent removed, and the residue taken up in a small quantity of dry ether; the ether was removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. B. p., yield, analysis, etc. are recorded in Table I.

β -(*N'*-Piperidinoethyl or *N'*-morpholinoethyl)-*N'*-phenylcarbamoyl-(*N'*-alkoxypropyl)-amine.— *N*-Piperidino- or morpholino-ethylalkoxypropylamine (1 *M*) and phenyl isocyanate (1.1 *M*) were refluxed in dry benzene for 3 hours; benzene was removed, the residues were crystallised from petroleum ether, and recrystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and petroleum ether. M.p., yield, analysis, etc. are recorded in Table I.

β -(*N'*-Piperidinoethyl or *N'*-morpholinoethyl)-*N*-phenylthiocarbamoyl-(*N'*-alkoxypropyl)-amine.— Phenyl isothiocyanate (1 *M*) was added to *N*-piperidino- or *N*-morpholino-ethylalkoxypropylamine (1 *M*) in benzene and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hours; benzene was removed and the residues were crystallised from petroleum ether and then recrystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and petroleum ether. M. p., yield, analysis, etc. are recorded in Table I.

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